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MYCOTIC KERATITIS : IN VITRO AND IN VIVO
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ABSTRACT

Fungal keratitis is a severe ocular infection secondary to accidental macro or microscopic trauma of the cornea. Dramatic increase of this infection was recorded along with the spread of antibiotic and heavy corticosteroids. This fungal disease is difficult to treat because of the scarcity of efficacious topical and systemic drugs. We evaluated in vivo and in vitro effectiveness of two surfactants on fungal isolates from patients with fungal keratitis. The results showed that Cetrimide have more broad spectrum antifungal activity in vitro, more penetration and more persistence ratio in eye tissues, and have little histopathological effects on corneal layers in comparison to Povidone Iodine.

INTRODUCTION

Fungal keratitis was first scribed by Leber in 1879, and was considered as one of the major causes of infectious keratitis in tropical areas. The severity of mycotic keratitis is due to misdiagnosis, absence of a definite shape for infected lesion, absence of a topical antifungal agent prepared for ocular use, nephrotoxicity of available systemic drugs and great difference between their in vitro and in vivo effects ⁽¹⁾.

Nevertheless, the study of chemotherapeutic agents with low toxicity and high fungicidal activity is required ⁽²⁾.

Various specific antifungal agents have been used polyenes, amphotricin 0.15% with varying degree of success. However, these specific antifungal agents are not usually available in developing countries and are expensive. Even in U.K. they are not available commercially for topical use but only in designated referral centers ⁽³⁾.

Povidone Iodine (PVP-I) is an antiseptic agent that is used as a topical ocular antimicrobial agent appears promising, particularly in developing countries, although studies are required to determine its efficacy in treating different ocular infections and to identify any side effects associated with frequent use ⁽⁴⁾.

In a study about the primary interactions of three quaternary ammonium compounds including Cetrимide with blastospores of *Candida albicans*, it was suggested that the anti-adherence effects are due to either direct interaction with, or steric blockage of adhesions on the blastospore surface ⁽⁵⁾.

AIM OF THE WORK

The aim of this work is to evaluate the antifungal efficacy of two available surfactants (Cetrимide and Betadine PVP-I) against mycotic keratitis causing fungi in vitro, and their ocular penetration and persistence in different ocular tissues of rabbit's eyes to obtain cheap available topical broad spectrum antifungal drugs with least side effects with recording any histopathological corneal changes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

(I) Preparation of antifungal agents :

We have been chosen two surfactants :

- 1- Cetrimide (Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide) (Sigma Fine Chemicals, U.S.A.).
 - 2- Betadine (Povidone iodine PVP-I) 5% (Nile Pharma, Cairo. ARE under license by Mandi, Pharma. AG Basel, Switzerland).
- Then we prepared 5% solution of each one in distilled water under sterile condition, freshly and used in this work through one hour as instructed by the manufacture.

(II) Preparation of tested fungi and cultures :

- 1- Tested fungi were isolated from patients' eyes clinically diagnosed as fungal keratitis, according to Magro et al. ⁽⁶⁾, purified and identified (Fig. 1).
- 2- Stock suspensions of vegetative cells (for yeast fungi) and spores (for filamentous fungi) were prepared in sterile distilled water and concentration of suspensions were standardized at 56×10^4 CFU /ml for each fungus ⁽¹⁾. Fungi were isolated from patients before treatment initiation so the different sensitivities shown by the isolates were not related to previously acquired drug resistance.
- 3- Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) medium (Nassar Pharmaceutical Industry Co.) was prepared and autoclaved. Then fungal suspensions (0.5 ml) were mixed with nutrition media (10 ml) in each sterile Petri-plate at 50 °C, homogenized, let to solidify at room temperature and incubated at 35 °C.

Fig. (1)

Example of two patients with Mycotic Keratitis and their cultures features

- A. Patient with *Aspergillus flavus* infection**
- B. Culture feature of *Aspergillus flavus***
- C. Patient with *Candida albicans* infection**
- D. Culture feature of *Candida albicans***

(III) General survey of antifungal activity of both surfactants in vitro:

- 1- Sterile Whatmann no. 1 filter paper discs (Whatmann international Ltd. Maidston, U.K.) were soaked in both Cetrimide and Povidone iodine solutions of 5% concentration for one hour till saturation.
- 2- A disc of each drug was put centrally on one of last seeded plates with different fungi.
- 3- All plates were incubated at 35°C for 36 hour, then inhibition zones were measured for both surfactants against all tested fungi using the inverted microscope ⁽¹⁾. The test was repeated twice and the mean of the inhibition zone was taken .

(IV) Persistence and Antifungal activity of both surfactants in vivo:

1- Experimental animals : 10 albino rabbit twins about 1 kg weight each were adapted for laboratory conditions within 3 days before work according to ARVO statement for use of experimental animals in Ophthalmology and Vision research.

2- Drug application :

- i- Freshly prepared 5% solution of each surfactant was applied topically on 5 rabbit's right eyes as 3 drops ($25\mu l$) in each eye.
- ii- One rabbit for each drug was scarified after 1/2, 1, 2, 6, 24 hours, eyes were dissected simultaneously
- iii- For each drug, at each time of sacrifice, tear film equally weighted specimens from conjunctiva, peripheral cornea, central cornea, aqueous, and iris, were isolated from dissected eyes under aseptic conditions.

3- Antifungal and % persistence test :

- i- We have been chosen only 2 fungi for in vivo tests: *Candida albicans* as a yeast, and *Aspergillus flavus* as a filamentous fungus, their plates were prepared as shown previously as they are the most common isolates although a wide range of other genera are found ⁽⁴⁾.
- ii- Each isolated tissue was put on one yeast- seeded plate and one filamentous fungus-seeded plate. Then all plates were incubated at 35°C for 36 h. and inhibition zones were measured.
- iii- Lastly the mean % drug persistence of both surfactants in each tissue for both yeast and filamentous fungi were calculated in comparison against in vitro inhibition zones of the same fungi ⁽⁷⁾.

(V) Control test :

1- Positive control : All in vivo tests were compared with in vitro plates of the same used fungi.

- 2- Negative control : Untreated eye tissues of rabbit's left eyes were put on fungi-seeded plates, showed no antifungal activity .

(VI) Histopathological examination :

Effects of both surfactants were investigated on different layers of corneal tissues as follow :

- 1- Two albino rabbit twins of 1 kg weight were adapted for lab. conditions for 3 days before this work .
- 2- Drug application : 3 drops of each tested solution were applied in the right eyes while the left eyes of both rabbits were untreated and used as a control for histopathological examinations.
- 3- Rabbits were sacrificed after 2 hours, some of the fixative material (10% formaldehyde) was injected in anterior chamber by 27 gauge needle to maintain the endothelium ⁽⁴⁾.
- 4- Cornea of treated and control eyes were excised with a rim of sclera by making 360 incision just behind the limbus, fixed in 10% formaldehyde solution for the rest of 24 hours.
- 5- Intact fixed corneal samples were dehydrated in alcohol, xylon, impregnated in paraffin, then stained with hematoxylin and eosin.
- 6- Different layers of cornea were examined by light microscopy for all treated and non-treated eyes.

RESULTS

(I)- fungicidal activity of both surfactants in vitro.

Inhibition zones of 5% cetrimide and betadine against different fungi in vitro are shown in table 1 & Fig. 2, 3. Cetrimide 5% showed mean inhibition zone diameter against various fungi isolates greater than PVP-I 5%.

(II)- Fungicidal activity and % persistence of drugs in vivo :

Percentage persistence of both surfactants in different eye tissues (in vivo) at different times after application are shown from tables 2-7 and corresponding curves. Fig.4 shows inhibition zones of ocular tissues containing the tested drugs.

As regard *C. albicans* there was statically insignificant difference between 2 surfactant as regard tear film (TF), conjunctiva (Conj.) central cornea (C.C) and peripheral cornea (CP) after half an hour.

PVP-I showed no effect on *A. Flavus* even after half an hour. PVP-I showed no tissue persistence in both aqueous humor and iris in compare with Cetrimide throughout all the time.

PVP-I showed tissue persistence which were higher than Cetramide in the tear film, conjunctiva, central cornea and peripheral cornea in *C. Albicans* group after 30 minutes and one hour.

The tissue persistence for PVP-I was lost for all tested tissue after two hours with relative decrease of the persistence for Cetrimide. The range of tissue persistence of Cetrimide is nearly stable and stay for a long time.

Table (1) : In vitro antifungal activity of both tested surfactants (inhibition zones diameters in cm).

Fungus	5% Cetrimide	5% Betadine
<i>C.neoformans</i>	1.6	0
<i>A.niger</i>	0.7	0.4
<i>A.fumigatus</i>	0.9	0.5
<i>A.flavus</i>	2.1	1.2
<i>Sclerotinia sp</i>	2.3	1.2
<i>Trichoderma sp</i>	1.9	0
<i>C.albicans</i>	2	0.6
<i>Cladosporium sp</i>	2.8	1.2
<i>Fusarium sp</i>	1.5	0

Fig. (2) : Inhibition zones in centimeters of both surfactants against different fungi.

Fig. (3) : Inhibition zones "in vitro results".

Fig. (4) : Inhibition zones "In vivo results".

Table (2) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 30 minutes.

Eye tissue	Cetrimide		Betadine	
	<i>C. albicans.</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>	<i>C. abl.</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
T.F.	67	62	92	-
Conj.	65	60	66	-
C.C	46	56	73	-
C.P.	49	58	75	-
AQ	30	28	-	-
IRIS	32	30	-	-

Fig. (5) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 30 minutes

Table (3) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 1 hours .

Eye tissue	Cetrimide		Betadine	
	<i>C. alb.</i>	<i>A. fla.</i>	<i>C. abl.</i>	<i>A. fla.</i>
T.F.	46	43	80	-
Conj.	35	40	72	-
C.C.	26	36	50	-
C.P.	29	38	80	-
AQ.	10	8	-	-
IRIS.	12	10	-	-

Fig. (6) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 1 hour.

Table (4) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 2 hours.

Eye tissue	Cetrimide		Betadine	
	<i>C. alb.</i>	<i>A. fla</i>	<i>C. abl.</i>	<i>A. fla.</i>
<i>T.F.</i>	28	26	-	-
<i>Conj.</i>	22	2	-	-
<i>C.C.</i>	18	22	-	-
<i>C.P.</i>	21	28	-	-
<i>AQ.</i>	9	16	-	-
<i>IRIS.</i>	12	9	-	-

Fig. (7) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 2 hours.

Table (5) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 6 hours.

Eye tissue	Cetrimide		Betadine	
	<i>C. alb.</i>	<i>A. fla</i>	<i>C. abl.</i>	<i>A. flavus</i>
T.F.	0	12	-	-
Conj.	0	17	-	-
C.C.	13	18	50	-
C.P.	16	23	-	-
AQ	7	26	-	-
IRIS	12	5	-	-

Fig. (8) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 6 hours .

Table (6) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 24 hours.

Eye tissue	Cetrimide		Betadine	
	<i>C. albi</i>	<i>A. fla</i>	<i>C. abl.</i>	<i>A. fla.</i>
<i>T.F.</i>	0	7	-	-
<i>Conj.</i>	0	10	-	-
<i>C.C.</i>	10	15	-	-
<i>C.P.</i>	8	13	-	-
<i>AQ.</i>	4	32	-	-
<i>IRIS</i>	10	0	-	-

Fig. (9) : % persistence of both surfactants in eye tissues for yeast & filamentous fungi after 24 hours.

Table (7) : Average of % persistence of Cetrimide and Betadine in central cornea and aqueous after different periods of applications, in relation to their antifungal activity against both tested groups of fungi.

Eye tissue	Cetrimide	Betadine	Time
C.C.	51	36.5	1/2 h.
AQ.	29	-	
C.C.	31	25	1h
AQ.	9	-	
C.C.	20	-	2h
AQ.	12.5	-	
C.C.	15.5	-	6 h.
AQ.	16.5	-	
C.C.	12.5	-	24h.
AQ.	19.5	-	

Fig. (10) : Average of % persistence of Cetrimide and Betadine in central cornea and aqueous after different periods of applications, in relation to their antifungal activity against both tested groups of fungi.

(III) Histopathological results :

Light microscopy of the normal control rabbit's (Fig.11, i) cornea showed epithelial five layers of cells on basement membrane; with regularly arranged stromal lamellae with keratocytes frequently seen and lastly Descemet's endothelial complex with no vacuolation.

Light microscopy of the intact cornea with Povidone Iodine 5% application in the right cornea showed after two hours epithelial desquamation (Fig.11, iii) with minimal stromal edema.

Light microscopy of the intact cornea with Cetrimide 5% application in the right cornea showed after two hours minimal epithelial change with minimal stromal edema (Fig.11, ii).

DISCUSSION

Over years various therapeutic agents regimens have been preside, but non has shown constant effectiveness in achieving a clinical and fungicidal cure. Our objective was to set up a simple method of testing fungi against 2 surfactants to give broad indication of its potential efficacy. Our method is cheep, easily reproducible and requires only very basic materials and technical skills.

In agreement with Rahman (1998) ⁽⁸⁾, we believe that the effectiveness of an antifungal agent on fungi is of clinical value when it causes the complete destruction of both vegetative cells and spore form.

We evaluated the efficacy of two surfactants of PVP-I and Cetrimide 5% on various fungal isolates from patients with proven cases of fungal keratitis in vivo and in vitro.

Martin et al. (1995) ⁽⁴⁾, mentioned that Povidone Iodine showed a good response at all concentrations in vitro for all fungi, this agree with our results in vitro for 5% concentration except *trichoderma*, *fusarium* and *C. neoformans*.

Fig. (11) Histopathological findings
i-Control cornea ii-Cornea treated with Cetrimide iii-Cornea treated with Betadine

However Martin and Johnson et al ⁽⁴⁾ , mentioned that in a small pilot study conducted in India to assess clinical efficacy for fungal corneal ulcers, Povidone Iodine was ineffective .

Povidone iodine has been shown to be effective against *Aspergillus niger* introduced into rabbit eye ⁽⁹⁾ .

Our results showed that PVP-I was effective in vivo against strains of Candidiasis but the filamentous group showed resistance that may be due to spores formation.

Cetrimide have more broad spectrum antifungal activity in vitro, more penetration and more persistence ratio in eye tissues, with minimal histopathological effects on corneal layers.

Betadine have narrow spectrum, low penetration, low tissue persistence, and cause severe edema for corneal stroma and epithelium.

CONCLUSION

Cetrimide 5% could be used safely in treatment of mycotic keratitis, while Betadine may be only used as a pre-operative disinfectant.

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